

Environmental Identity Economics:

An Application to Farmers' Pro-Environmental Investment Behaviour

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Abstract

This study proposes an environmental identity economics theory that can improve our understanding of pro-environmental behaviour. We test the potential of the theory by analysing farmers' decisions to invest in renewable energy production using a hybrid choice model. Our findings illustrate that farmers with a strong environmental identity require little financial incentive to invest. Furthermore, lower compensation is found to be sufficient to induce farmers with a strong environmental identity to commit to more binding investment contracts. Our findings stress the need for differentiated designs of agri-environmental programmes and mechanisms that enhance farmers' environmental identity.

JEL codes: D91;Q18; Q42

Keywords: Environmental identity, identity economics, hybrid choice model, agri-environmental practices, choice experiment

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1. Introduction

Agriculture is one of the most important anthropogenic contributors to environmental challenges such as greenhouse gas emission (GHG) and deterioration in water quality. The need to integrate rigorous environmental and climate objectives into agricultural policies to tackle the impacts of agriculture on environment has been argued for so long. For instance, the environmental impact of agriculture has been one of the main topics that influenced the debate in the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) for the period 2021-2027 ([Lampkin et al., 2020](#)). In the CAP, a combination of mandatory and voluntary approaches are in use to regulate agriculture's impact on environment ([European commission, 2018](#); [Lampkin et al., 2020](#)). In the mandatory part, there are basic environmental requirements that farmers must fulfil to receive agricultural subsidies. In the voluntary part, CAP consists of two schemes: i) agri-environmental schemes using rural development programs (Pillar 2), ii) Eco-schemes, a newly introduced scheme, which aims to incentive more sustainable farm management using direct payments (Pillar 1) ([European commission, 2018](#)).

From standard economic point of view, a rational farmer will choose to participate in a voluntary agri-environmental practices (agri-environmental schemes or Eco-schemes), if and only if the participation payment outweighs the cost of participation. However, there is an increasing amount of literature that recognizes that not only financial motive but also non-pecuniary motives influence farmers' participation in agri-environmental practices (e.g., [Gosling & Williams, 2010](#); [Greiner & Gregg, 2011](#); [Mzoughi, 2011, 2014](#); [Sattler & Nagel, 2010](#); [Warren, Burton, Buchanan, & Birnie, 2016](#); [Wauters & Mathijs, 2013](#)). Using data from French fruit-growers and vegetable producers, [Mzoughi \(2011\)](#) find that farmers social and moral concerns drive their decision to

adopt integrated crop protection and organic farming. [Warren et al. \(2016\)](#) also find that farmers' decision to adopt innovative agri-environmental practices such as short rotation coppice willow is strongly affected by farmers' social-cultural identity related to life style and farming. They further argued that even large potential profits are not enough to persuade many farmers to adopt short rotation coppice willow. There is also a growing research that aims to integrate behavioural and experiment economics into agri-environmental research to design effective agri-environmental programs that mitigate environmental and climate challenges (see [Palm-Forster, Ferraro, Janusch, Vossler, & Messer, 2019](#) for a review). Moreover, in reviewing the behavioural factors that influence farmers' decisions to adopt environmentally sustainable practice, [Dessart, Barreiro-Hurlé, and van Bavel \(2019\)](#) demonstrate that considering behavioural factors improves economic analyses of farmer decision-making, and argue that it can lead to more effective agri-environmental policies.

In this study, the focus is on (environmental) identity, a non-financial factor that has received very little or no attention in the agri-environmental research but which may have a paramount importance in the design of agri-environmental programs. Looking at the comprehensive review by [Dessart et al. \(2019\)](#), it is apparent that previous studies have paid very little or no attention to the role of identity on farmers decision to adopt pro-environmental agricultural practices. An identity is defined as set of meanings attached to self that serve as a standard or reference for who one is ([Burke, 1991](#)) and the term 'environmental identity' is often used to link individual's identity with the environment. According to [Clayton \(2003\)](#) an environmental identity is defined as 'one part of the way in which people form their self-concept: a sense of connection to some part of the nonhuman natural environment, based on history, emotional attachment, and/or similarity, that affects the way we perceive and act toward the world; a belief that environment is important to us

and an important part of who we are'. Clayton (2003) describes environmental identity as a motivating force that shapes our environmental thinking and behaviour. Similarly, van der Werff, Steg, and Keizer (2013) describes environmental (self) identity as the extent to which you view yourself as the type of person who acts pro-environmentally. In this paper, we use both conceptualizations and the term environmental identity is used to reflect whether a farmer sees oneself as part of nature (environment) and/or identifies oneself with a specific agri-environmental program.

Research on the relationship between individual's identity and natural environment is gaining attention in the field of environmental psychology and sociology (e.g. Hinds & Sparks, 2009; Leary, Toner, & Gan, 2011; Olivos & Aragonés, 2011; Ries, Hein, Pihu, & Armenta, 2012; Schultz & Tabanico, 2007; Stets & Biga, 2003) and environmental identity has proved to be an important predictor of pro-environmental behaviour (e.g. Fielding, McDonald, & Louis, 2008; Kiesling & Manning, 2010; Whitmarsh & O'Neill, 2010). For example, using an environmental identity scale developed by Clayton (2003), a qualitative study by Kiesling and Manning (2010) shows that environmental identity significantly predicts ecological gardening behaviour. Furthermore, some qualitative studies indicate that environmental identity is more influential than other factors in shaping environmental behaviour (Stets & Biga, 2003; Whitmarsh & O'Neill, 2010). Similarly, Whitmarsh and O'Neill (2010) show that pro-environmental self-identity is a significant behavioural determinant over and above variables of Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) for carbon offsetting behaviour amongst the UK public. There are also very few studies that demonstrate the role of identity on farmers' adoption of pro-environmental practice (Gosling & Williams, 2010; van Dijk, Lokhorst, Berendse, & de Snoo, 2016). For instance, Gosling and Williams (2010) find that connectedness to nature strongly increases farmers' vegetation

protection behaviour. In addition, using an extended version of TPB, [van Dijk et al. \(2016\)](#) demonstrate that self-identity is the most dominant predictor of farmers intentions to perform agri-environmental measures.

This paper combines the environmental identity concept of environmental psychology and sociology with the identity economics concept to explore thoroughly the effect of environmental identity on farmers' agri-environmental practices and its economic implications. [Akerlof and Kranton \(2000\)](#) introduced the concept of identity in economics. Identity economics captures the idea that who people are and how they think of themselves is vital to the economic decisions they make. In identity economics, external forces do not sustain the norms. According to [Akerlof and Kranton \(2010\)](#) 'people follow norms because they want to do so. They internalize the norms and adhere to them'. Akerlof and Kranton show that identity shapes individuals economic choices and outcomes with applications in economics of education, gender and organization ([Akerlof & Kranton, 2002, 2005, 2010](#)). For example, they demonstrate that it is not the incentive system but whether workers identify themselves with an organization that is most influential for an organization to succeed.

Thus, this paper develops an identity economics theory of environmental behavior (environmental identity economics theory) following [Akerlof and Kranton \(2005\)](#) and [Akerlof and Kranton \(2010\)](#) to explore farmers' decision to engage in agri-environmental practices. We test the theory empirically with an application to farmers' pro-environmental investment behaviour using data on farmers' participation decision in a manure based collective biogas investment. Manure based biogas production directly or indirectly contributes to multiple environmental and climate objectives such as transition to renewable energy, reduction in greenhouse gas emission, sustainable agricultural waste management and reduction of nutrient leaching to the aquatic

environment (Al Seadi et al., 2008; Al Seadi, Stupak, & Smith, 2018; Bundgaard & Kofoed-Wiuff, 2014). These advantages of biogas production are closely linked with the future CAP climate and environmental objectives (European commission, 2018). In the empirical investigation, we use a discrete choice experiment method to elicit farmers' willingness to invest in collective biogas production and furthermore environmental identity and biogas related identity indicators are collected and linked to features of the biogas investment scheme using an integrated choice and latent variable model (ICLV). The remainder of the paper is structured as follow: section 2 gives the theoretical framework of the study; section 3 provides a brief overview of the case study, study design and data used in this study; section 4 describes the empirical modelling used in this study; section 5 presents the results and discussion of the study and section 6 gives the concluding remarks of the study.

2. Theoretical framework

In this section, an identity economics theory of environment (environmental identity economics theory) is developed following Akerlof and Kranton (2005) and Akerlof and Kranton (2010). We assume two types of actors: farmers and the government with the environment at the intersection. We assume that the government supports farmers with a subsidy when they voluntarily participate in agri-environmental practices such as that of the agri-environmental-climate measures (Pillar 2) and Eco-schemes (Pillar 1) in the CAP. We use an expected utility framework, where farmers are utility maximisers. From the viewpoint of standard economics, farmers gain utility from income (including subsidy) that they receive and lose utility from the effort they exert² on (implementation cost of) an agri-environmental activity, which means that it is a balance between applied effort

² For sake of simplicity, we assume that cost of implementation of and effort exerted on agri-environmental activities are the same and are used interchangeably. The higher the effort the higher cost or viceversa.

(cost of implementation) and expected financial gains. In other words, farmers participate in agri-environmental activity if and only if their expected financial gain outweighs their cost (the effort they exert). The regulator can influence farmers' effort on agri-environmental practice by paying more subsidy. Now, we introduce environmental identity (E) into the utility function to understand the role it plays. In doing so, following [Akerlof and Kranton \(2005\)](#) and [Akerlof and Kranton \(2010\)](#), we add three components of environmental identity to the standard utility function: i) environmental identity categories, ii) norms and ideals for each category and iii) environmental identity utility, which is the gain when agri-environmental actions conform to norms and ideals, and the loss if they do not.

Based on their environmental identity, we categorize farmers into two: 1) farmer with a strong environmental identity (H) i.e. a farmer with a strong sense of connection to the natural environment and/or particular environmental activities, 2) a farmer with a weak environmental identity (L) i.e. a farmer that does not identify or weakly identifies him or herself with the environment and/or particular environmental activities. In the *norms and ideals of the categories*, we suppose that a farmer with a strong environmental identity is highly concerned about environmental issues as the regulator does and thinks s/he should undertake environmental activities on behalf of the regulator. Thus, the ideal action for a farmer with a strong environmental identity is to exert high effort on an agri-environmental practice. On the contrary, a farmer with a weak environmental identity mainly thinks about him or herself and cares less about environment and agri-environmental practices. The norm for such type of farmer is to exert the least possible effort in agri-environmental activities. In the third component, *environmental identity utility*, we assume that a farmer with a strong environmental identity gets personal utility (environmental identity utility) from undertaking agri-environmental activities and thus, loses utility if s/he exerts

no or low effort on agri-environmental practice. Conversely, a farmer with a weak environmental identity loses utility if s/he exerts high effort on agri-environmental practices.

Mathematically, following [Akerlof and Kranton \(2005\)](#) the utility of a farmer that incorporates environmental identity utility can be described as:

$$U(X, C; E) = U(X) - U(C) + I_E - t_E |C^*(E) - C| \quad (1)$$

where U is the farmer's utility, X captures different features of an agri-environmental program. (In the context of the our study, it captures attributes of the collective biogas investment such as contract flexibility, contract length, subsidy). $U(X)$ is utility generated from the favorable features of the program, C is the actual effort or cost level of the farmer and $U(C)$ is disutility from cost of implementation of or effort exerted on agri-environmental activities. $C^*(E)$ is the ideal cost from or effort on an agri-environmental practice, E is the farmer's environmental identity category (H or L), I_E is the farmer's environmental identity utility from being in a category, t_E captures the importance of acting according to the ideal, and $t_E |C^*(E) - C|$ is then the disutility from diverging from the ideal effort or cost level for category E .

Given the above stated conditions, the first order condition for the utility function with respect to effort (actual and ideal) can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial C} > 0, \frac{\partial U}{\partial C^*(E)} < 0; \text{ if } C < C^*(E) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{NB: } C^*(L) < C^*(H)$$

Equation (2) shows, that if the actual effort on agri-environmental activities is lower than the ideal effort, a farmer gains utility when his actual effort gets closer to ideal effort but an increase in ideal effort results in a loss in utility.

What is then the implication of the environmental identity economics model described above for agri-environmental contracts? The model indicates that a farmer who strongly identifies with the environment and particular agri-environmental activities acts in the best interest of the authorities by participating in pro-environmental activities and exerting a high level of effort and the reverse is true for a farmer with weak environmental identity. This in turn affects the effectiveness of agri-environmental contracts. Below, we will present the model implications on two common and crucial elements of agri-environmental contracts: subsidy and contract flexibility.

Subsidy is one of the key aspects of agri-environmental contracts that farmers require to participate in voluntary agri-environmental practices. For example, in the CAP, European farmers are provided a subsidy to encourage them to participate in agri-environmental measures and eco-schemes using rural development programs and direct payments respectively ([European commission, 2018](#)). Following the above formulation, for a farmer with strong environmental identity less monetary subsidy is required to induce high effort environmental action. In contrast, a farmer who has a weak connection with the environment and particular agri-environmental activities requires high monetary subsidy to participate and exert high level of effort on agri-environmental activities. Failing to account for environmental identity may then result in over-subsidizing a farmer with strong environmental identity or under-subsidizing a farmer with weak environmental identity. Thus, on the one hand, paying low monetary incentives for individuals with weak environmental identity may lead to limited involvement in agri-environmental practice. On the other hand, paying high monetary incentives for farmers with strong environmental identity who could have participated in environmental schemes with little incentive wastes public spending.

Contract flexibility is another vital feature in agri-environmental contracts, which can be described in terms of a possibility to cancel agri-environmental contracts or duration of contracts. From the regulator or government perspective, long-term and stable commitments are needed to achieve climate and environmental targets. However, previous studies indicate that farmers want short and flexible contracts because farmers wish to avoid potential uncertainties regarding future costs and benefits (Broch & Vedel, 2011; Christensen et al., 2011). Thus, short and flexible contracts would allow them to pursue other and more profitable investment options. As aforementioned, a farmer with strong environmental identity derives utility from undertaking agri-environmental practices and works to tackle environmental issues on behalf of the regulator. Thus, for a farmer with a strong environmental identity, a less flexible contract is enough to induce high effort environmental action. In other words, lower compensation payment is enough to induce a farmer with a strong environmental identity to accept less flexible agri-environmental contracts. In contrast, for a farmer with a weak connection with the environment and particular agri-environmental activities, highly flexible contracts are needed to induce a high intensity of participation in agri-environmental activities.

In the empirical part of this paper, we attempt to test this with an application to Danish farmers' manure based collective biogas investment choice. It is well understood that to measure perfectly all variables accounted for in the environmental identity model (equation 1) is not an easy task. However, some of the variables may be possible to measure at least imperfectly using survey questions. Hence, in this study farmers' environmental identity is measured by their response to statements from environmental identity scale (EID) developed by Clayton (2003) and biogas production related identity. We then link environmental identity statements to farmers' manure

based biogas investment choice and to each feature of the investment scheme (e.g., subsidy, flexibility) using ICLV.

3. Case Study and Data

The agri-environmental practice of interest in the empirical work of this study is manure based collective biogas investment. Manure based biogas production directly or indirectly contributes to multiple environmental, climate, energy and agricultural objectives that include transition to renewable energy, reduction in greenhouse gas emission, sustainable agricultural waste management and reduction of nutrient leaching to the aquatic environment (Al Seadi et al., 2008; Al Seadi et al., 2018; Bundgaard & Kofoed-Wiuff, 2014). EU rural development policy includes economic measures that encourage production and use of renewable energy from agricultural biomass (European Commission, 2010, 2018) because it plays a substantial role in meeting EU environment, climate and energy objectives. The advantages of biogas production mentioned are also closely linked with the climate and environmental objectives of the new CAP. Biogas production could contribute to at least two of three CAP specific objectives that concern environment and climate: *'contribute to climate mitigation and adaption as well as sustainable energy'*, and *'foster sustainable development and efficient management resources such as water, soil and air'* (European commission, 2018).

This study uses a discrete choice experiment (DCE), a stated preference (SP) method, to elicit farmers' preference for manure based collective biogas investment. DCE is based on Lancaster's characteristic theory of value where an individual's utility is determined by attributes of a good or service (Lancaster, 1966). DCE is becoming an increasingly popular approach in the agri-environmental research and contributes to the design of agri-environmental policies (Broch & Vedel, 2012; Christensen et al., 2011; Hasler et al., 2019; Ruto & Garrod, 2009). On top of

addressing specific policy questions, [Hanley and Czajkowski \(2019\)](#) claim that SP methods such as DCE can be a useful tool to examine conceptual ideas such as influence of behavioural levers (e.g., social norms) and the role of deep drivers of heterogeneity (e.g., emotion and personality) on individual choices, which have broader implications for economics and behavioural sciences.

The data used in this study was collected from Danish farmers. Farmers were asked to choose alternative manure based biogas investment options in a repeated choice experiment with several attributes (see, [Table 1](#) for the descriptions of the attributes used in the study). A D-efficient fractional factorial design, optimized for multinomial logit model, was implemented in Ngenex ([ChoiceMetrics, 2012](#)) to produce choice sets with three alternatives (two unlabelled biogas investment options and a ‘none’ option).

Table 1. Description and levels of a collective biogas investment attributes

Attribute ³	Description	Levels	Type
Number of partner farmers	Number of farmers that participate in a collective biogas investment	1, 3, 6,10,15,20	Continuous
Flexibility to cancel partnership	Possibility to cancel a partnership or to retire from a collective biogas plant	At any time After one year After 5 years Not at all	dummy coded

³ Note: the bold levels are used as base level in the estimation. The subsidy attribute expressed in percentage is converted into monetary units using an average investment cost of 350 DKK/ton ([Bundgaard & Kofoed-Wiuff, 2014](#); [Jacobsen, Laugesen, Dubgaard, & Bojesen, 2013](#)).

Distance to a collective biogas plant (km)	Distance to a collective biogas plant	0.5, 1, 3, 6, 10,15, 20	Continuous
Contract length (year)	Length of purchase contract between a collective biogas plant and biogas buyers	1, 5, 10 and no contract	dummy coded
Start-up consultancy	Administrative, technical and other assistances from a municipality, agricultural advisory bodies or others to start a collective biogas investment	Yes No	dummy coded
Subsidy (%)	Investment grant to participate in a biogas investment and is expressed as a percentage of an investment cost for a biogas plant	5%, 12%, 15%, 20%,24%,30%	Continuous

The survey was administered nationwide by a market research and Consultancy Company called Aspecto A/S using a web-based survey. The target farmers of the survey were livestock farmers as the main purpose of the study was to examine farmers' manure based biogas investment decision. The sampling strategy also considers farmers' geographical distribution and type of livestock. The survey only includes farmers who own above 75 livestock units (LSU) because farmers with low LSU largely represent hobby farmers for whom biogas investment is not relevant. The questionnaire comprised several questions such as a farmer's current situation regarding biogas, choice experiment part, environmental identity statements, and farmer and farm characteristics. In the choice experiment part, respondents were provided with six choice sets, each choice consisted of two manure based biogas investment options and a third alternative with the 'none' option.

As previously mentioned, farmers were asked a number of general environmental identity ($I_1 - I_4$) and biogas specific identity (I_5 & I_6) questions to empirically explore the role of environmental identity on farmers' pro-environmental investment behaviour. The general environmental identity indicators were selected from EID developed by Clayton (2003). Respondents' answers were collected on the five-point Likert scale for each of the general environmental identity and biogas specific identity statements ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The following six items of environmental identity indicators were used:

I_1 : When I am upset or stressed I feel better by spending time in nature

I_2 : I think of myself as part of nature, not separate from it

I_3 : I would feel that an important part of my life was missing if I was not able to get out and enjoy nature from time to time

I_4 : I do not pay much attention to environmental problems

I_5 : To engage in environmentally friendly activities such as biogas production is an important part of who I am

I_6 : I am not the type of person who is oriented towards engaging in biogas production

The analysis of this study is based on 461 farmers each answering six choice sets totalling 2766 observations.

4. Empirical Modelling

An integrated choice and latent variable model (ICLV) (aka hybrid choice model, HCM) is used to link environmental identity statements to farmers' manure based biogas investment choice. HCM is formally developed by Ben-Akiva et al. (2002) and bridges the gap between discrete choice models and behavioural theories by representing explicitly unobserved elements of a decision making process (Abou-Zeid & Ben-Akiva, 2014; Ben-Akiva et al., 2002). HCM has the

potential to integrate discrete choice models with latent variable models. Hence, it is often referred to as an integrated choice and latent variable model (ICLV). Latent variables are factors that are unobserved directly, however, the analyst can get measures of these variables in terms of other variables called indicators (Daly, Hess, Patrui, Potoglou, & Rohr, 2012). Indicators are manifestations of respondents' latent variables. Environmental identity is unobserved unlike socio-economic and demographic characteristics; hence, it is treated as a latent variable. There are statistical issues when indicators are used directly in utility functions (Daly et al., 2012). The major issues are: 1) answers to psychometric questions are not direct measures but functions of underlying latent attitudes, and using psychometric measures directly can lead to measurement error. 2) The indicators may be correlated with unobserved factors, which can lead to endogeneity bias. The main advantages of HCM are explicit modelling of unobserved heterogeneity, gain in statistical efficiency, behavioural realism and prediction (Abou-Zeid & Ben-Akiva, 2014). Despite these benefits and increasing use of HCM in various disciplines, recent studies have questioned if the effort exerted on estimating the HCM model is deserving compared to the benefits, particularly, when the purpose is prediction (Chorus & Kroesen, 2014; Klojgaard & Hess, 2014; Mariel & Meyerhoff, 2016). However, these studies recognize the distinctive advantages of HCM over standard discrete choice models in disentangling unobserved heterogeneity and understanding the behavioural insight of a choice making (Mariel & Meyerhoff, 2016; Vij & Walker, 2016).

Mathematically, the HCM model consists of structural equations and measurement equations. Structural equations express causal or behavioural relationship of variables whereas the measurement equations describe observed variables as function of unobserved or latent variables. We illustrate the entire model graphically in Figure 1. The boxes and ellipses represent observed

variables (indicators) and unobserved variables (latent variables), respectively. Directed arrows illustrate the estimated coefficients and the error terms. The solid arrows represent causal relationships while dashed arrows represent measurement relationships.

Figure 1. The structure of the integrated choice and latent variable modelling framework

4.1. Structural model

The latent variable for environmental identity (D_n^*) is denoted as: .

$$D_n^* = \gamma'Z_n + \eta_n \quad (3)$$

where Z_n is a vector of farm and farmer characteristics for farmer n . The farm and farmer characteristics used in the analysis include gender, age, farming experience, off-farm activity, farm size and membership in environmental organization. γ is a vector of estimated parameters capturing the effect of these variables Z_n on the latent variable D_n^* , and η_n is a random error term which follows standard normal distribution across individuals.

In HCM, the utility function for alternative i in choice situation t for an individual n is given by:

$$U_{int} = V(X_{int}, D_n^*; \beta, \tau) + \varepsilon_{int} \quad (4)$$

where X_{int} represents the attributes of the biogas investment, β are estimated parameters that contain the effect of these attributes X_{int} on utility, τ is an estimated parameter which captures the impact of the latent variables on utility, and ε_{int} is the random component of the utility function. The latent environmental identity enters the utility function in interaction with the parameters of all attributes of collective biogas investments and their respective parameters of interest.

4.2. Measurement model

Indicators of environmental identity are functions of the latent environmental identity

$$I_n = \lambda'D_n^* + v_n \quad (5)$$

Where I_n is a vector of indicators of environmental identity of a farmer, λ is a vector of estimated parameters that measure the impact of the latent variable, D_n^* , on indicators of environmental identity I_n , v_n is vector of error terms.

The specification of the error term (v_n) determines the behaviour of the measurement model and it is dependent on the nature of the indicator. The responses to the environmental identity indicators are collected using a five-point Likert response scale (strongly disagree to strongly agree) and thus, the responses are ordered choices. Therefore, the measurement equations can be given by ordered logit structure instead of a continuous measurement equation (Daly et al., 2012). For example, for a single environmental identity indicator k with five levels, the structure can be described as follows:

$$I = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } -\infty < D^* \leq t_1 \\ 2 & \text{if } t_1 < D^* \leq t_2 \\ 3 & \text{if } t_2 < D^* \leq t_3 \\ 4 & \text{if } t_3 < D^* \leq t_4 \\ 5 & \text{if } t_4 < D^* \leq \infty \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where t_1, t_2, t_3 and t_4 are threshold parameters for the indicator.

The likelihood of the observed value of the indicator I_{nk} in an ordered logit structure is written as:

$$L(I_{nk} | t, \lambda, D_n^*) = \sum_{S=1}^5 I(I_{nk} = S) \left[\frac{\exp(t_{k,S} - \lambda'_{Ik} D_n^*)}{1 + \exp(t_{k,S} - \lambda'_{Ik} D_n^*)} - \frac{\exp(t_{k,S-1} - \lambda'_{Ik} D_n^*)}{1 + \exp(t_{k,S-1} - \lambda'_{Ik} D_n^*)} \right] \quad (7)$$

where S is a response to the indicator k which ranges 1 to 5. The likelihood for all the observed indicators for an individual, I_n , is given by:

$$L(I_n | t, \lambda, D_n^*) = \prod_{k=1}^K L(I_{nk} | t, \lambda, D_n^*) \quad (8)$$

Discrete choice model:

Choice among the set of J biogas investment options (alternatives) at choice situation t is modelled by assuming that farmers maximize utility. This implies that we can express the choice indicator, y_{int} , as a function of the utilities of the alternatives based on utility maximization, i.e. a respondent n chooses alternative i at choice situation t if the $U_{int} > U_{jnt}$.

Hence, the likelihood of the observed sequence of choice for respondent n is denoted as:

$$L(y_{int} | \Omega, \tau; X_{in}, D_n^*) = \prod_{t=1}^T \frac{\exp(\beta_n' X_{in} + (\lambda' D_n^*) X_{in})}{\sum_j \exp(\beta' X_{in} + (\lambda' D_n^*) X_{in})} \quad (9)$$

Thus, the log likelihood function for the stated choice model and the observed indicators of latent variables under mixed logit model is denoted as:

$$LL = \sum_{n=1}^N \ln \iint (y_n | \cdot) L(I_n | \cdot) g(\beta | \Omega) g(D_n^* | \cdot) d\beta dD_n^* \quad (10)$$

A random parameter hybrid choice model (RPHCM) is used to estimate the model in this paper. The model is estimated in R using the flexible choice modelling package *Apollo* (Hess & Palma, 2019), and using 500 draws based on Modified Latin Hypercube Sampling (MHLS) (Hess, Train, & Polak, 2006). For the sake of simplicity, we assume a normal distribution for all the parameters of the attributes of biogas estimated in the model. Furthermore, in order to make identification of hybrid choice models possible, we normalize the variance of the error terms of the latent variables to one (Daly et al., 2012). The model is estimated in willingness to accept-space (Scarpa, Thiene, & Train, 2008).

5. Results and Discussion

The response to environmental identity questions shows that 64% of the respondents agree with the statement ‘when I am upset or stressed I feel better if I spend time in nature’ (Figure 2). More than 90% of the respondents think of themselves as part of nature and not separate from it and a similar fraction of farmers agree that they would feel that an important part of their life was missing if they were not able to get out and enjoy nature. Over 80% of the farmers in the sample disagree with statement that ‘I don’t pay much attention to environmental problems’. The result of the response to biogas specific identity questions indicates that around 47% of farmers disagree with statement ‘I am not a type of person who is oriented towards engaging in biogas production’ and 28% agree that to engage in environmentally friendly activities such as biogas production is an important part of who they are.

Figure 2. Farmers’ response to environmental identity indicators

The full estimation results of the structural, measurement and discrete choice components of the RPHCM are reported in [Table 2](#). Let us start by interpreting the results from the measurement and

structural components of the model (Panel B and Panel C in [Table 2](#)), before we proceed to the results from discrete choice component. The results from the measurement equation part of the model help us to understand the link between latent (unobserved) environmental identity and the response to the environmental identity statements. The results of the measurement model show that the latent environmental identity has the expected sign and is significantly reflected on almost all the indicators of the environmental identity. As can be seen from Panel C of [Table 2](#), latent environmental identity is positively and significantly linked with farmers' responses to statements D_1 , D_2 , D_3 , and D_5 while it is negatively and significantly reflected on a response to statement D_4 .

Moreover, the structural equation component of the model allows us to understand the effect of farm and farmer characteristics on the latent environmental identity. The results of the structural component of the model as can be seen from Panel B of [Table 2](#), indicate that some farmer groups are more likely to influence the latent environmental identity than others are. For example, all else the same, farmers who participate in off-farm activities are more likely to show higher environmental identity than those who do not. In addition, farmers who are members of environmental organizations are more likely to have higher environmental identity than non-members are.

Returning to the results of the discrete choice component of the model in Panel A of [Table 2](#), we are mainly interested in the last column of the panel which contains the parameters for the interaction between the latent environmental identity and the parameters for the different features of the collective biogas investment. However, before we proceed to the interpretation and discussion of these results, we start by briefly presenting the results from the main effects estimates

of the choice model. The first two columns in Panel A of [Table 2](#), display farmers' mean and standard deviation of the WTA estimates for the attributes of collective biogas investments. The estimation result shows a positive and significant effect of subsidy indicating that that an increase subsidy motivates farmers to participate in a collective biogas investment. This is in line with economic theory. In addition, the WTA estimates for the non-monetary attributes show that farmers are willing to accept reductions in subsidy for an additional number of partner farmers a flexibility to cancel partnership contract, and to receive a free start-up consultancy. Furthermore, farmers require an additional compensation when the distance to collective biogas plant gets further away from their farm. The standard deviation estimates of WTA also confirm a large preference heterogeneity for most of the parameters of the attributes.

Table 2. The results of the RPHCM model

Panel A: Discrete choice component (WTA-space, in DKK/ton)			
	Main effects		Interactions
	Mean	Std. deviation	Environmental Identity
	-3.98	-148.605***	-28.839***
ASC(none)	(18.609)	(0.515)	(9.151)
	4.173***	5.664***	-0.032
Number of partner farmers	(0.257)	(0.364)	(0.386)
	52.503***	-28.768	-40.506*
Flexibility to cancel-at anytime	(0.227)	(17.546)	(21.28)
	73.527***	-6.406	-26.87***
Flexibility to cancel-after one-year	(2.628)	(9.135)	(7.619)

	45.171***	-16.793***	-17.302***
Flexibility to cancel –after five years	(2.061)	(0.369)	(0.557)
	-1.78***	3.726***	0.657**
Distance biogas plant	(0.315)	(0.35)	(0.255)
	6.845**	-13.091***	-6.514***
Start-up consultancy	(2.998)	(2.11)	(0.93)
	10.202***	-15.026***	2.07***
Contract length-one year	(2.683)	(0.485)	(0.601)
	-7.508***	55.241***	-1.891
Contract length-five year	(0.539)	(7.637)	(2.712)
	12.442***	21.778***	34.34**
Contract length-ten year	(0.257)	(0.273)	(15.45)
	0.017***	0.037***	-0.006***
Subsidy	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.002)

Panel B: Structural component

	Environmental Identity (D*)
	-0.327
Gender	(0.32)
	-0.007
Age	(0.009)
	0.008
Farming experience	(0.008)

Off-farm activity	0.284**
	(0.134)
Medium farm size	0.316
	(0.248)
Large farm size	0.31*
	(0.176)
Member of environmental organization	0.47**
	(0.238)

Panel C: Measurement component

	Environmental				
	Identity (D*)	Threshold1	Threshold2	Threshold3	Threshold4
I_1	0.984***	-4.564***	-3.386***	-0.845***	1.931***
	(0.175)	(0.414)	(0.298)	(0.224)	(0.225)
I_2	1.8***	-6.078***	-5.186***	-3.55***	0.827**
	(0.343)	(0.572)	(0.512)	(0.338)	(0.353)
I_3	1.834***	-5.493***	-5.051***	-3.58***	0.102
	(0.269)	(0.555)	(0.498)	(0.441)	(0.338)
I_4	-0.943***	-1.107***	1.765***	2.765***	4.985***
	(0.166)	(0.192)	(0.231)	(0.277)	(0.402)
I_5	0.528***	-2.147***	-1.061***	1.107***	3.455***
	(0.162)	(0.201)	(0.16)	(0.138)	(0.251)
I_6	-0.224	-1.798***	-0.095	1.252***	2.711***
	(0.15)	(0.137)	(0.101)	(0.121)	(0.224)

Panel D: Model characteristics

Number of individuals	461
Number of observations	2766
LL(start)	-8429.43
LL(final, whole model)	-5504.309
AIC	11148.62
BIC	11563.38
Estimated parameters	70

Note: Standard error estimates are in parentheses. ***,** and * indicate statistical significance at 1%, 5% and 10%. The sign of the standard deviation estimates are irrelevant.

The main purpose of the empirical work of this study is to test the environmental identity economics framework outlined in section 2. In the empirical modelling, this is demonstrated by interacting latent environmental identity with the parameter estimates of the attributes of the collective biogas investment and alternative specific constant of the ‘none’ option (ASC). The results are reported in the last column in Panel A of Table 2. The estimates show preference heterogeneity across respondents and thus, the results allow us to test whether preference for the different attributes of the agri-environmental practice and ASC vary depending on the farmers’ environmental identity. The interaction of the ASC and the latent environmental identity shows a negative and significant effect signifying that farmers with strong environmental identity have higher disutility for the ‘none’ option of the biogas investment alternative. Farmers with strong

environmental identity are willing to accept a subsidy a reduction of 29 DKK/ton to avoid the 'none' situation.

Parameter estimates of the interaction between environmental identity and parameters of subsidy and contact flexibility are of our primary interests since these attributes are some of the common and popular features in the design of agri-environmental contracts. The interaction effect estimates, Panel A of [Table 2](#), show a significant and negative parameter estimate for the interaction between environmental identity and subsidy estimates indicating that respondents with strong environmental identity have a less positive reaction to receiving investment grant to participate in pro-environmental investment. In other words, the result shows that a respondent with strong environmental identity requires less subsidy to engage in pro-environmental investment such as collective biogas investment. This finding is consistent with the theoretical approach described in [section 2](#), which implies that farmers who identify themselves with the environment are willing to participate and exert effort in environmentally friendly activities with little incentive. Conversely, farmers who weakly identify with environment and particular agri-environmental practice (e.g., biogas production) place higher emphasis on the size of subsidy rather than striving to achieve environmental, energy and agriculture goals. This is in line with [Akerlof and Kranton \(2005\)](#) who suggest that individuals who do not identify themselves with an organization seek to play with incentive systems rather than to meet the organization's goal.

This finding (and explanation) may provide an answer to why there is limited participation of farmers in agri-environmental practices and provide a perspective for agri-environmental policies. Failing to account for environmental identity of farmers coupled with subsidy system which is based on a uniform subsidy (per unit subsidy same for all farmers) may be one reason for low

adoption of environmentally friendly agricultural practices. The implementation of a uniform subsidy may not bring the intended outcome since it fails to take heterogeneity of agents into account (e.g., farmers environmental identity category) (Lichtenberg, 2002). Under a uniform subsidy, farmers with weak environmental identity may be under-subsidized meaning that farmers with weak environmental identity may find the subsidy offer insufficient. Thus, this may in turn result in a low involvement of this category of farmers in agri-environmental practices. On the other hand, when a uniform subsidy is implemented, farmers with strong environmental identity may be over-subsidized as they would have participated with little incentive and this may result in an excessive public spending.

The results in Panel A of Table 2 also show that the interaction between latent environmental identity and the parameters of the non-monetary attributes (WTA estimates) are significant for most of them. For example, in relation to the flexibility to cancel collective contract, the result shows that respondents with strong environmental identity have a less positive reaction to the flexibility to cancel a collective contract meaning that they value the possibility to cancel contract less. On average, flexibility to cancel a contract is valued 45-73 DKK/ton but farmers with strong environmental identity value the opportunity to cancel a contract 17-40 DKK/ton less than the average estimates. In other words, lower payments or compensations are enough to induce farmers with strong environmental identity to accept less flexible contracts. The interactions between latent environmental and length of contract estimates (another feature of contract flexibility) also show that a farmer with positive environmental identity places higher value on long-term contracts over having no contract. This implies that respondents with high environmental identity are willing to enter into long-term commitment with buyers of biogas output. Previous studies claim that uncertainty about future benefits and costs is the main reason for farmers to ask for short and

flexible contracts (Broch & Vedel, 2012; Christensen et al., 2011). Thus, the most likely explanation for the lower valuation of contract cancelation options and higher valuation of longer commitments by farmers' with strong environmental identity is that they are less worried about future benefit and cost uncertainties. These findings are consistent with theoretical predications in section 2.

Furthermore, the result in Panel A of Table 2 confirms that farmers with strong environmental identity have a less positive reaction to free start-up consultancy meaning that they place less value on free start-up consultancy. Little or no payment is enough to induce farmers' with strong environmental identity to enter into a contract without start-up consultancy. Moreover, the parameter estimate of an interaction between latent environmental identity and parameter estimates of distance shows a positive and significant estimate signifying that farmers with strong environmental identity have a less negative reaction to distance to collective biogas plant or vice versa. This means that farmers with strong environmental identity demand less compensation to travel longer distance and take part in a collective biogas investment. Distance to biogas directly translates into transportation cost and transportation of raw materials (manure) to a biogas plant is a costly part of the biogas production, which accounts about 40% of the total biogas production cost (Jacobsen et al., 2013). Thus, the less negative reaction to distance reaffirms that farmers with strong environmental identity are less concerned by the financial burden.

To sum up, the empirical findings are consistent with the environmental identity economics theory developed in section 2. The findings of the study show that environmental identity has a powerful influence on farmers' decision to participate in agri-environmental practice. Lower subsidy is enough to induce farmers with a strong environmental identity to participate in agri-environmental

practice. Furthermore, a lower compensation is needed to induce farmers with strong environmental identity to accept less favourable contract features such as less flexible contracts, long-term commitments, long travel distances and contracts without start-up consultancy. These findings provide important insights to the agri-environmental research and design of agri-environmental contracts, which will be briefly discussed in the next section.

6. Conclusion

This paper develops an environmental identity economics theory following [Akerlof and Kranton \(2005\)](#) and [Akerlof and Kranton \(2010\)](#) to understand farmers' decision to engage in agri-environmental practices. We employ an empirical strategy using a hybrid choice model with an application to farmers manure based collective biogas investment decision based on a data from 461 Danish livestock farmers to test the theory. To our knowledge, this study is the first to investigate the economic analysis and implications of environmental identity with a focus on farmers' agri-environmental practice. Our findings suggest that environmental identity is a crucial aspect of farmers' decision to participate in agri-environmental practice. Environmental identity influences the amount of subsidy that farmers require to participate in agri-environmental investment. Lower subsidy is enough to induce farmers with a strong environmental identity to participate in pro-environmental investment. Furthermore, lower compensation is enough to induce farmers with a strong environmental identity to accept less favourable features of agri-environmental contracts such as less flexible contracts, long-term commitments, long travel distances and contracts without start-up consultancy.

The results of this study provide information to support agri-environmental policy initiatives aimed at choosing the right incentive system as it is clear that a uniform incentive system does not suit

all farmers. Policy makers need to introduce a unique incentive strategy that takes the heterogeneity of the farmers' into account i.e. low and high requirement of incentive by strong and weak environmental identity of farmers respectively. For example, an auction based scheme could be used to implement a differentiated subsidy and it is expected that farmers with strong environmental identity would give low bids while farmers with weak environmental identity would make high bids, reflecting higher incentives. A related policy implication is that not only subsidy but also the other design features of a contract need due consideration. It may be relevant to provide farmers with different types of contracts with various design features. For example, farmers with strong environmental identity may choose to enter into stable and long-term commitments, which is of paramount significance to meeting environmental, and climate objectives. Furthermore, another important policy implication is that policy makers need to consider investing in the enhancement of farmers' environmental identity, developing the environmental vision of agri-environmental schemes and the alignment between environmental identity and scheme objectives. If this were successfully implemented, maybe more farmers would identify with more environmentally friendly agricultural practices with less financial incentive. However, it is equally relevant to consider the cost and benefit of investing in environmental identity. Further work is required on other agri-environmental applications in order to have solid understanding about the influence of environmental identity on adoption of agri-environmental practices.

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